

ADAPTIVE ENVIRONMENTS FOR ROBOTIC ASSISTED NEURO-LIMBIC RECOVERY BY REASSESSING MANAGEMENT IN AVIATION ACCIDENTS CASE

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Abstract

Purpose – This paper examines the potential of robotic-assisted neuro-limbic recovery in the context of aviation accidents, combined with the importance of professional training in medical robotics.

Methodology/approach – Rare but documented cases are presented, the Cecilia Cichan, the single survivor of a plane crash at the age of four, and the James Polehinke, co-pilot of a crashed flight. In this article, alternative approaches for robotic assistance in neuro-limbic recovery are considered, with a methodology that involves analyzing data from aviation accident injuries to explore how robotic rehabilitation could have helped.

Findings – Robotic-assisted rehabilitation offers significant advantages in the recovery process of motor and neurological functions, determined by precise conducted repetitive movements, real-time monitoring and customized adjustments, with great help and facilities extension for therapists.

Research limitations/implications – The limited availability of detailed patient data and rapidly evolving technologies may need for more accreditation data and demonstrations.

Practical implications – Large-scale implementation of robotic assisted rehabilitation technologies requires investment in training of medical staff and hospital infrastructure. This article contributes to understanding of how new founding may transform neuro-rehabilitation practices.

Originality/value – Aviation accidents cause severe injuries such as multiple fractures, burns, brain damage and amputations, requiring complex medical interventions and long-term rehabilitation. Advanced rehabilitation technologies are key to improving the quality of life of survivors, as demonstrated in the case studies of Cecilia Cichan and James Polehinke.

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Key words: robotic assisted rehabilitation, aviation accidents.

Introduction

Neuro-Limbic Rehabilitation aims to rehabilitate people with severe limb injuries and neurological damage, often caused by serious accidents, including aviation accidents. In the last years the robotic assistive technologies have revolutionized the field, offering new hope for improved recovery.

This paper reveals some interdisciplinary studies considering the combination of engineering, managerial and medical explored aspects within the identification of the robotic-assisted recovery potential, highlighting the importance of professional training in medical robotics. In addition to the inhouse research, two case studies were consider illustrating the potential impact of robotic assisted technologies on patients and for guiding future research. In this paper, the authors reviewed the Cecilia CICHAN and the James POLEHINKE recovering processes.

Applied Methodology

The considered methodology includes the data analyze the aviation accident injuries, observing what was done in terms of rehabilitation during that period and what could have been achieved with today's technology.

Being happened before the existance of the robotic assisted rehabilitation to comparative analysis is applied first to highlights the differences in severity and type of injuries, followed by the comparative analysis of the applied rehabilitation process with the actual possibilities. The actual considered robotic assisted rehabilitation process is revealed from the existing specialized literature (academic articles and research reports) and from the original research.

Research Implications

There are 3 keys elements that characterise the alternative recovering treatment processes by using assistive robotics:

- the robots itself and the treatment that can be applied
- the benefits of the new kind of applied treatment
- the perspectives of improvement that this medical technology tackle

Robotic Treatment in Neuro-Limbic Recovery was developed to enhance the doctors and physiotherapists capabilities in assisting patients during the recovery of motor and neurological functions. These technologies include:

- Hand and finger robotics to help recover fine motor skills.
- External orthoses, which stabilize limbs and assist movements.
- Robotic exoskeletons, which support patients' natural movements.
- FES (Functional Electrical Stimulation) which activates paralyzed muscles with electrical pulses or epidural electrical stimulation (EES) for spinal cord injuries.
- Anti-gravity treadmills that allow walking or running with partially supported body weight, reducing joint stress, external prosthesis which can replace not only the body part, but also the function, soft robots which can diminish the frozen effect in Parkinson disease.

The benefits that may be acquired from Robotic Rehabilitation offer many advantages, even in this infant stage of its development. Among that the most mentioned are:

- Precise repetition of movements – which leads to a decrease in the recovery process over time, precision provides us with the assurance that tissue limits are not exceeded, the repetition of movements leads to an increase in tissue resources (resistance, strength, control), all of which led to better functionality and ensuring efficient neuroplastic recovery.
- Real-time monitoring and adjustment – We can observe the patient's vital functions in real-time during therapy, we can observe the strength, speed, and resistance that the patient applies, the rehabilitation robot can detect compensatory movements and intervene to improve them and through all this, the patient is actively involved, creating a phenomenon of biofeedback. From all of this, it emerges that robotic rehabilitation is a treatment that offers us objective monitoring and adapts to the patient's progress.
- Enable therapists to work in parallel with several patients – more patients can benefit from therapy in a shorter time and therapists can focus on other aspects of rehabilitation such as patient assessment and patient education.
- Improved patient motivation - interactivity and gamification of exercises increase adherence to the rehabilitation program, adherence that many patients lack for various reasons (immobility, depression, loss of autonomy, and functional independence). The patient's motivation will increase when they notice that all these aspects improve through robotic rehabilitation, thus the patient will be much more involved in the therapy, resulting in a favorable prognosis.

As the research activities continue, new perspectives open up:

- ❖ Rapid device development - According to "Perspectives and Challenges in Robotic Neurorehabilitation" (Riccardo Iandolo et al., MDPI), exoskeletons and FES have revolutionized neuro-motor recovery through real-time monitoring and adjustment of treatments. Combinations with personalized training regimens and brain-machine interfaces improve movement control and neuroplasticity.
- ❖ Usability of robotic and virtual reality devices - The article "A systematic review on the usability of robotic and virtual reality devices in neuromotor rehabilitation: patients' and healthcare professionals' perspective" published by BMC Health Services Research provides a detailed perspective on the usability of robotic and virtual reality devices, highlighting their strengths and limitations in clinical practice. Robotic devices are perceived as safe and effective in improving physical independence and psychosocial well-being.
- ❖ Innovations in Robotic Medicine - Dr. Mathew Thomas and Rachel Rutledge from Mayo Clinic emphasize, in an interview on innovationexchange.mayoclinic.org, the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration and continued innovation to the success of robotics programs. Mayo Clinic, through its Division of Military Medicine, supports veterans and active-duty members of the armed forces through educational programs and innovative research.
- ❖ Inclusion of rehabilitation robots in hospital centers - Over the years, the CESTER team has managed to design, model, build, test, and develop various rehabilitation robots for certification, both for the upper and lower limbs, with some of them already having significant studies conducted in hospitals. Later on, these robots can also be adapted for implementation in the patient's home.

These insights and benefits highlight the enormous potential of robotic rehabilitation technologies in transforming medical practices and improving patients' quality of life.

Cases Description

Air disasters, marking significant loss of life, induce major perception and safety crises, affecting reputation and confidence in aerospace. Analysis of the last 50 years most tragic aviation accidents demonstrates the extent of the impact on passenger and crew safety:

- 1974, Turkish Airlines Flight 981 – crashed, caused by a cargo door malfunction, resulting in the deaths of 346 people.
- 1980, Saudia Lockheed L-1011 Tristar - fire on-board fire was taking 301 lives
- **1987, Northwest Airlines Flight 255** - crashed near Detroit Metropolitan Airport on takeoff, 154 people killed; the only survivor was a four-year-old girl.
- 1988, Iran Air Flight 655 - accidentally destroyed by an U.S. Navy aircraft, killing 290 individuals
- 1996, Air Africa - an overloaded plane crashes in a populated area in Kinshasa, within the tragedy 227-348 people were killed
- 1996, Charkhi Dadri air – crashed in New Delhi, being the deadliest air collision, with a death toll of 349
- **2006. Delta Airline, Bombardier Canadair Regional Jet 100ER, Comair Flight 5191** - crashed on takeoff in Lexington, Kentucky, while attempting to take off from Blue Grass Airport in Fayette County, the runway was too short for a safe takeoff, causing the aircraft to overrun the end of the runway before it could become airborne, killing all 47 passengers and two of the three crew. It was the second-deadliest accident involving the CRJ100/200; two years earlier, China Eastern Airlines Flight 5210 claimed 55 lives.
- 2024, Tokyo Haneda Airport - five occupants of a Japanese Coast Guard aircraft were killed in a collision with a Japan Airlines passenger plane, but all 367 passengers and 12 crew members of JAL516 were safely evacuated due to the good training of the flight crew.

These accidents highlight the crucial importance of safety and reliability in aviation. Each tragic incident emphasizes the need to implement strict safety measures and rigorous regulations to protect both passengers and crew, highlighting the long-term consequences on human life. Fortunately, aviation accidents are not very often, and each case is analyzed in detail to make safer the aviation transportation. But when happens are dramatic casualties and therefore special attention must be ensured for the survivors. The rare occurrence but the intense intervention and specialization demonstrates the need for HRT (Human Resource Training), as was evidenced also in the Japan Airlines JAL516 case on the Tokyo Haneda Airport in 2024.

Importance of Human Resource Training

Effective aviation crisis management requires continuous training of aerospace personnel, ensuring rapid response times and well-defined strategies for emergency situations. This is especially essential in cases of serious accidents that will require short, medium and long-term medical care. Essential aspects of regular training:

- Training through practical simulation exercises, organized regularly with different simulated scenarios coupled with exercises that prepare staff to react effectively in emergency situations. Like FAA (Federal Aviation Administration) simulation programs, where complex scenarios prepare crews for various crisis situations.
- Effective internal and external communication, with clear established and effective channels of communication both within the organization and with external entities, including authorities and the public. The ICAO (International Civil Aviation Organization) crisis communication training programs are essential for effective coordination during incidents.

- Risk assessment and scenario planning constantly, conduct risk assessments and develop action plans for various possible scenarios. EASA (European Union Aviation Safety Agency) aviation risk management programs are models for developing well-structured contingency planning.
- Flexibility and innovation to adapt quickly to change must be cultivated within organizations, with innovation to adapt quickly to new challenges and conditions.
- Continuing education programs in medical robotics and rehabilitation at leading institutions such as Mayo Clinic demonstrate the importance of ongoing, adaptive education for improved patient outcomes.

Considering the Mayo Clinic example the Post-Accident Recovery is strongly impacted by the technological developments and the clinical staff training. The proper training of medical and aerospace personnel can directly influence patients' post-accident recovery:

- Mayo Clinic's robotic rehabilitation programs, with integrate training in the use of exoskeletons and other robotic devices, allowing therapists to provide personalized and effective treatments, increasing the chances of patients for rapid and full recovery
- Immersive educational programs for healthcare professionals that include training in emergency simulations and the use of advanced technologies, improve staff response and treatment skills, contributing to the effective recovery of aviation accident victims
- Interdisciplinary collaboration and training programs, including physicians, engineers and robotics experts to ensure a holistic approach to treatment and recovery, maximizing the benefits of robotic rehabilitation technologies.

Through continued investment in staff training and education, the aerospace and medical sectors can significantly improve post-accident recovery, thereby reducing the long-term impact on patients' lives.

Medical Impact of Aviation Accidents

Aviation accidents often cause severe injuries, requiring complex medical interventions and long-term rehabilitation processes. Resulting trauma can include multiple fractures, burns, brain injuries and amputations, each presenting specific challenges in recovery. These traumas highlight the importance of well-structured rehabilitation programs and advanced rehabilitation technologies to improve the survivor's quality of life, locomotor as well as psychological.

Considered Cases

1. Cecilia CICHAN

The single survivor of 1987a plane crash, at the age of four who suffered severe burns and fractures. In 2024 she is 41, married and living under the name Cecelia Crocker.

Additional clarifications & Accident Details

Cecilia's medical history was largely secret, making it difficult to obtain detailed information about her recovery journey. Cecilia CICHAN benefited from a dedicated team that addressed her psychological and social needs, although specific details are scarce.

- Third-degree burns over 30% of the body, requiring skin grafts
- A fractured left leg, requiring insertion of a pin into the femur bone
- A concussion and a fractured collarbone

- ✓ Severity and types of injuries – Above is described the order in which these injuries would be treated, the approach requiring a multidisciplinary team to maximize treatment effectiveness, with burns taking precedence because they can cause various complications, both through potential infection and delayed scarring.
- ✓ Technologies that could have been used – Unfortunately, during that period, there were no robot-assisted therapies tailored to assist Cecilia's rehabilitation. However, if we consider the case in the present day, rehabilitation robots would come to aid not only in conventional physical therapy but also in psycho-social applications. In the present, there are rehabilitation robots that assist in the rehabilitation of burns, like Amadeo they can prevent scar formation that could lead to functional impairment. Additionally, there are rehabilitation robots which could be used for fracture rehabilitation, like CESTER rehabilitation robots, both for the upper and lower body which alleviate pain, improve motor function and reduce recovery time. For psycho-social support, there are robots with diverse objectives. from providing comfort and companionship (Sony's Aibo, Hasbro's Joy for All Companion Pets, PARO), reducing the feeling of loneliness, stimulating the young one through online games, video chats, suggesting sporting activities or enabling a two-way communication from distance between the patient and the caretaker

Conclusion for the Robotic Physical-Psychological-Social Assistance

Robotic rehabilitation technologies, such as external orthoses, could have help in her mobility recovery. However, these interventions seem excessive for her specific needs and are not essential for long-term recovery. Robotic assistance for burn rehabilitation, which is extremely painful and delicate, is another potential but limited application. Psychological and social support was crucial to her recovery.

2. James POLEHINKE

Was the co-pilot, as pilot flying at the time of the accident Comair Flight 5191 and was the sole survivor but who suffered multiple fractures and amputations following the plane crash.

Additional clarifications & Accident Details

- Brain damage causing memory loss
- Amputation of the left leg and surgical repair of the right leg
- Two spinal fractures, broken bones in the left leg, right leg and right hand
- A series of fractures from face to legs, including a complex fracture of the pelvis and a collapsed lung
- ✓ Severity and types of injuries - James' injuries are significantly more severe than CECILIA affecting multiple body systems and requiring comprehensive rehabilitation, in the short term, but also in the long term, some of them changing his quality of life completely.
- ✓ Technologies that could have been used – In this case, rehabilitation technology not only plays a role in restoring a previously used function but also intervenes in replacing a lost function caused by lower limb amputation. By the year 2006, there were already certain technological devices that could provide added benefits in the rehabilitation process, such as The Controlled Brake Orthosis for motor deficits resulting from spinal cord injury, and various mechanical orthoses for transfemoral amputation. In the present day, due to technological advancements, rehabilitation robots could significantly improve James's quality of life. In the acute stage, they could assist in therapy by aiding in transfers and mobilizing his lower limb at the bedside. In the chronic

stage, current external prostheses could help him resume activities such as climbing stairs or running, activities which James is currently unable to perform.

Robotic Physical Assistance

Robotic assistance can greatly benefit James, offering solutions such as improved external orthoses and mobile ramps for home use. These technologies can help in both acute hospital settings and chronic home care, improving his mobility and quality of life.

Types of robotic systems that could be helpful to James:

For the rehabilitation of the left lower limb – CESTER robot RAISE or RECOVER for mobilizing the entire limb, thus immobilizing the pelvis and eliminating risks of refracture. Initially in passive mode, followed by transition to active mode.

For the rehabilitation of the amputated limb - in the acute stage until stump healing, conventional physiotherapy is recommended. After healing of the scar tissue, an external prosthesis can be applied, for example, the Utah Bionic Leg. This lightweight orthosis can be beneficial for walking as well as for ascending and descending stairs, actions that James cannot perform due to the stairs not being adapted to his condition.

Conclusion for the Robotic Physical-Psychological-Social Assistance

He currently uses a wheelchair and is unable to climb stairs, highlighting the need for advanced rehabilitation technologies. Still, with all of this, James has adapted his environment with hand-powered bikes, adaptive skis and various ramps, demonstrating his resilience and potential for additional robotic assistance in daily living.

Unfortunately, James primarily relies on a wheelchair for mobility, likely due to vertebral fractures. His condition underscores the importance of a multidisciplinary team in implementing a robotic system adaptable to the patient's conditions. Currently, there is no exoskeleton or robotic system that is adaptable to both spinal cord injury and amputation. The ReWalk robot could be helpful, provided it could be coordinated with the amputated lower limb. All of these systems, can integrate James back in society, without having a physical disability.

And for the psychological aspect, James could benefit from remote psychological therapy through video. Additionally, a robot could listen to him, analyze the information received from James, and relay it to the medical team.

Comparative Analysis & Conclusions

The comparison between Cecilia Cichan and James Polehinke reveals significant differences in the severity and types of injuries, as well as the applicability of robotic rehabilitation technologies (Table 1).

Table 1 of Comparative Cases

Aspects	Cecilia Cichan	James Polehinke
Type of injury	Third-degree burns, leg and clavicle fractures	concussion Multiple fractures, amputation, brain injury
Rehabilitation needs	Skin grafts, orthopaedic interventions	Complex orthopaedic interventions, mobility support
Rehabilitation technologies	External orthoses, anti-gravity treadmills	Enhanced external orthoses, mobile ramps, manually operated bicycles
Psychological and social impact	Dedicated psychological and social support	Environmental adaptation for daily use and activities
Effectiveness of robotic rehabilitation	Limited - specific needs not aligned with current technologies	High - technologies have significantly improved mobility and quality of life

Conclusions

The differences in severity and types of injuries between Cecilia and James show that robotic rehabilitation technologies are more effective for extensive and varied injuries such as James'. In contrast, for cases like Cecilia's, where injuries are severe but do not require specific robotic interventions, traditional methods and psychological support may be more appropriate.

James' extensive and varied injuries present numerous opportunities for robotic assistance. Robotic rehabilitation technologies could have greatly improved mobility and quality of life, demonstrating significant potential in the recovery of patients with multiple and complex injuries.

This analysis highlights the importance of tailoring treatment and technology selection to each patient's specific needs.

Exoskeletons, external orthoses, anti-gravity treadmills, hand and finger robotics, and functional electrical stimulation (FES) offer diverse solutions for the recovery of motor and neurological functions.

Robotic rehabilitation allows for precise repetition of movements, real-time monitoring and adjustment of treatment, reduced physical effort for therapists and improved motivation for patients.

Continuous training of medical and aerospace personnel is crucial for effective crisis management and optimal use of robotic rehabilitation technologies.

Simulation and interdisciplinary training programs, such as those offered by the FAA, ICAO, EASA and Mayo Clinic, improve staff response and treatment skills, contributing to effective patient recovery.

Continued evaluation of the impact of long-term robotic rehabilitation technologies on patients' quality of life is needed.

Investigate how psychological support can be effectively integrated with robotic rehabilitation technologies to maximize benefits for patients.

Through further research and innovation in robotic rehabilitation, we can significantly improve the recovery and quality of life of patients with severe neuro-limbic injuries.

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